

**First record of *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch et Weißmair, 2007
from Bosnia and Herzegovina (Neuroptera: Sisyridae)**

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Abstract – *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch et Weißmair, 2007 (Neuroptera: Sisyridae) is reported from Bosnia and Herzegovina for the first time. The first habitus photos of adults of the species are published.

Key words – faunistics, distribution, aquatic insect, Balkan Peninsula

INTRODUCTION

Sisyra Burmeister, 1839 (Neuroptera: Sisyridae) is a genus of spongillaflyies of worldwide distribution. It is the only genus of the family in the Western Palearctic, represented by 9 species in the region according to current literature (ASPÖCK *et al.* 1980, 2001, RAUSCH & WEIßMAIR 2007). Seven species are known to occur in Europe; five of them, including *Sisyra dali* McLachlan, 1866, *Sisyra iridipennis* Costa, 1884, *Sisyra jutlandica* Esben-Petersen 1915, *Sisyra nigra* (Retzius, 1783) and *Sisyra terminalis* Curtis, 1854, have long been known from the continent (ASPÖCK *et al.* 1980, 2001), while two additional species, *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch et Weißmair, 2007 and *Sisyra corona* Rausch et Weißmair, 2007, were described relatively recently (RAUSCH & WEIßMAIR 2007).

The original description of *Sisyra bureschi* was based on specimens from Bulgaria, Croatia and Turkey (RAUSCH & WEIßMAIR 2007). Subsequently WEIßMAIR (2010) reported this species from Germany and CANARD *et al.* (2015a) from France.

PODLESNIK *et al.* (2017) recorded *Sisyra nigra* from Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina and *Sisyra terminalis* from Serbia, and predicted the occurrence of additional species in the Balkan Peninsula; these authors also summarised the previously known localities of *Sisyra bureschi*.

This work is based on examination of specimens deposited in the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM). Label data of the voucher specimens are given verbatim with explanatory information in square brackets. Identifications were based on ASPÖCK *et al.* (1980), RAUSCH & WEIßMAIR (2007), CANARD *et al.* (2015b), TILLIER & COPPA (2019), and THIERRY *et al.* (2020).

RESULTS

Sisyra bureschi Rausch et Weißmair, 2007 (Figs 1–2)

Material examined – Two males; “Yugoslavia: Mostar [= Bosnia and Herzegovina: Mostar], Buna part [= bank of the river Buna], 1973.VI.12., leg. Dr. H. Steinmann”.

Remarks – First record from Bosnia and Herzegovina. Whereas *Sisyra bureschi* is known to be distributed from France to Turkey, only a few local records are known from this broad area (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Germany). Further records of the species are expected from other European countries.

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Acknowledgements – I thank Dr. Dávid Rédei (National Chung Hsing University, Taiwan) for his valuable comments on the manuscript and Dr. Zoltán Vas (HNHM) for his help in translating German literature.

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YUGOSLAVIA:
Mostar, Buna part
1973.VI.12.
leg:Dr.H.Steinmann

Sisyra bureschi ♂
Rausch & Weißmair,
2007
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2

YUGOSLAVIA:
Mostar, Buna part
1973.VI.12.
leg:Dr.H.Steinmann

Sisyra bureschi ♀
Rausch & Weißmair,
2007
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Figs 1–2. *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch et Weißmair, 2007, voucher specimens
(photos by Viktória Szöke)

REFERENCES

- ASPÖCK H., ASPÖCK U. & HÖLZEL H. (in collaboration with RAUSCH H.) 1980: *Die Neuropteren Europas. Eine zusammenfassende Darstellung der Systematik, Ökologie und Chorologie der Neuropteroidea (Megaloptera, Raphidioptera, Planipennia) Europas. Band I+II.* – Goecke and Evers, Krefeld, 495+355 pp.
- ASPÖCK H., HÖLZEL H. & ASPÖCK U. 2001: Kommentierter Katalog der Neuropterida (Insecta: Raphidioptera, Megaloptera, Neuroptera) der Westpaläarktis. – *Denisia* 2: 1–606.
- CANARD M., THIERRY D., CLOUPEAU R., RAUSCH H. & WEIßMAIR W. 2015a: A spongillafly new to French fauna: *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch & Weißmair, 2007 (Neuropterida, Sisyridae). – *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de France* 120(1): 19–24.
<https://doi.org/10.3406/bsef.2015.2199>
- CANARD M., CLOUPEAU R., DANFLOUS S., GIACOMINO M., JACQUEMIN G. & THIERRY D. 2015b: Les Sisyridae d'Europe occidentale. Cartographie des espèces présentes en France. – *Revue de l'Association Roussillonnaise d'Entomologie* 24(4): 181–191.
- PODLESNIK J., KLOKOČOVNIK V., KLENOVŠEK T., JANŽEKOVIČ F. & DEVETAK D. 2017: First records of spongillaflies (Neuroptera: Sisyridae) in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, with notes on their occurrence in the Balkan countries. – *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 41: 164–169. <https://doi.org/10.3906/zoo-1508-48>
- RAUSCH H. & WEIßMAIR W. 2007: *Sisyra bureschi* nov. sp. und *S. corona* nov. sp. - zwei neue Schwammhafte und Beiträge zur Faunistik der Sisyridae (Insecta: Neuroptera) Südosteuropas. – *Linzer biologische Beiträge* 39(2): 1129–1149.
- THIERRY D., DURAND O. & CANARD M. 2020: Les Sisyridae (Neuropterida) de l'Ouest de la France. 3 - Clé iconographique pour l'identification des *Sisyra* Burmeister, 1839 d'Europe occidentale. – *Revue Française d'Entomologie Générale* 2(2): 33–37.
- TILLIER P. & COPPA G. 2019: Premières mentions de *Sisyra bureschi* Rausch & Weißmair, 2007 dans les bassins versants de la Seine et de la Meuse [Neuroptera, Sisyridae]. – *Ephemera* 21(2): 133–134.
- WEIßMAIR W. 2010: *Sisyra bureschi* und *S. dali* (Neuroptera: Sisyridae) neu in Südwest-Deutschland und weitere Beiträge zur Faunistik und Ökologie. – *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 54: 207–212.